

Appendix A: Online, Curriculum, and Policy Resources

National Curricular and Policy Frameworks

- Department of Education. (2023). *Primary Curriculum Framework*. Government of Ireland. <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/primary-curriculum-framework>
- Department of Education. (2022). *Schools Reconfiguration for Diversity: Transfer of Patronage of Primary Schools – Information for School Communities*. <https://assets.gov.ie/218518/3db727a9-8b1f-4342-af3d-0541a0581f83.pdf>
- Department of Education and Skills. (2015). *Framework for Junior Cycle*. Government of Ireland.
- Department of Education and Skills. (2016). *Wellbeing Policy Statement and Framework for Practice 2018–2023*. <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/>
- Department of Education and Skills. (2022). *National Strategy on Education for Sustainable Development: Towards 2030*. Government of Ireland.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (1999). *Social, Personal and Health Education: Teacher Guidelines*. NCCA.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2009). *Aistear: The Early Childhood Curriculum Framework*. NCCA.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2016). *Politics and Society: Leaving Certificate Specification*. NCCA.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2017). *Junior Cycle Civic, Social and Political Education (CSPE) Short Course*. NCCA.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2021). *Junior Cycle Philosophy Short Course Specification*. NCCA.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2023). *Primary Curriculum Framework for Primary and Special Schools*. NCCA.
- Teaching Council. (2020). *Cosán: Framework for Teachers' Learning*. Teaching Council of Ireland. <https://www.teachingcouncil.ie/>

Government and Agency Reports

- Department of Children and Youth Affairs. (2019). *National Participation Framework for Children and Young People in Decision-Making*. Government of Ireland.
- Department of Education and Skills. (2018). *Cumulative Report on DEIS Plan 2017–2020*. Government of Ireland.
- Department of Education and Skills. (2020). *STEM Education Policy Statement 2017–2026: Implementation Plan 2020–2026*. Government of Ireland.
- Government of Ireland. (2022). *National Strategy for Education for Sustainable Development: Towards 2030*. <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication>
- Oireachtas Library & Research Service. (2022). *Citizenship Education and Participation in Ireland: Parliamentary Briefing Paper*. Houses of the Oireachtas.
- UNESCO. (2021). *Global Citizenship Education: Topics and Learning Objectives*. UNESCO Publishing.

NGO and Support Organisations

- AONTAS. (2020). *Adult Learning for Active Citizenship*. AONTAS.

Centre for Human Rights and Citizenship Education (CHRCE). (2021). *Global Citizenship Education in Irish Classrooms: Teaching and Learning Resources*. Dublin City University.

Comhairle na nÓg. (2023). *Young Voices – Youth Consultation Reports*. Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth.

DevelopmentEducation.ie. (n.d.). *Global Citizenship and Human Rights Learning Resources*. <https://www.developmenteducation.ie>

Green-Schools Ireland. (2023). *Green-Schools Global Citizenship Programme*. An Taisce Environmental Education Unit.

Irish Aid. (2023). *Development Education Strategy 2023–2027*. Department of Foreign Affairs.

Léargas. (2022). *Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps in Ireland: Annual Report 2022*. Léargas.

PDST. (2023). *SPHE and Wellbeing Resources*. Professional Development Service for Teachers.

Trócaire. (2023). *Development Education Resources for Teachers*. <https://www.trocaire.org>

UNICEF Ireland. (2022). *Rights Respecting Schools Award (RRSA): Programme Guidance*. UNICEF Ireland.

International Frameworks and Conventions

Council of Europe. (2018). *Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture*. Council of Europe Publishing.

European Commission. (2018). *Council Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning (2018/C 189/01)*. Official Journal of the European Union.

European Commission. (2020). *Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027*. European Union.

United Nations. (1989). *Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC)*. United Nations General Assembly.

UNESCO. (2015). *Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. United Nations.

Other Supporting Materials and Websites

Education for Sustainable Development in Ireland: <https://www.education.ie/en/>

National Youth Council of Ireland (NYCI): <https://www.youth.ie/>

Ubuntu Network: <https://www.ubuntu.ie/>

Global Village Project: <https://www.globalvillageproject.ie/>

Hub na nÓg: <https://hubnanog.ie/>

Teaching Council Cosán Framework: <https://www.teachingcouncil.ie/en/teacher-education/cosan-framework/>